

THE HYDRO-INSULATING SOLUTIONS IN VERMICULITE STORE

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Abstract. In this article, the properties of thermal insulation solutions, which are one of the current exercises in construction works, were studied. Optimum compositions of thermal insulation solutions were worked out in vermiculite, which is widespread in the region of our country.

Key words: Thermal insulation, vermiculite, solution, superplasticizer.

ГИДРОИЗОЛЯЦИОННЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ В ВЕРМИКУЛИТОВОМ СКЛАДЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье были изучены свойства теплоизоляционных растворов, которые являются одним из актуальных занятий в строительных работах. Отработаны оптимальные составы теплоизоляционных растворов в широко распространенном в регионе нашей страны вермикулите.

Ключевые слова: Теплоизоляция, вермикулит, раствор, суперпластификатор.

Nawadays, many countries in the world do not consider thermal energy to be among the most expensive types of energy, because thermal energy is not renewable. Thermal energy is only used for heating. It is for this reason that most of the countries that we consider to be developed today have banned the construction of buildings and structures without the use of thermal insulation construction materials. It is possible to heat the walls of individual multi-story residential buildings by 30-40% [1]. Separate building materials are not effective in terms of thermal insulation. Special heat-insulating building materials are needed for the left-hand side. It is necessary to maintain the microclimate in the thermal insulation of the building with a tin hammer. After choosing the necessary wall construction materials for the building, it is necessary to choose the right solution. The reason is that the strength of solutions and the parameters of heat transfer should be close to the parameters of the material used in the wall construction. For example, if the thermal insulation of the wall construction is made of foam concrete-like material, in such a case, it is impossible to use apivai building solution, because the heat transfer of the apivai solution is 4-5 times more than the heat transfer of foam concrete. This affects the thermal insulation of the building. Apart from this, it is important that these solutions have a jeteral level of the required volume base. Based on the above, we can say that the use of vermiculite is one of the best ways to make thermal insulation solutions in the region of our country. In our Izertlew group, the effect of vermiclutide on construction solutions was determined by determining the optimal composition of thermal insulation construction solutions.

Keeping the air in the working part of the building is one of the actual issues in construction works today. This issue is one of the issues that must be resolved in the regions of our country. According to the data, it was found that most of the heat loss in buildings comes from protective

structures (~30%), roof coverings (~10%), mirrors (~25%), ventilation systems (~25%), and heat radiation (~10%) [2].

In insulated constructions, there are always places where heat is absorbed at a level that cannot be taken into account (places with cracks, crevices, etc.). All such places have a negative effect on the heat distribution of the building, and as a result, such places do not play the role of heat and cold air. We can give an example of such air ducts, such as plastered blocks, and even doors.

The solution of the solution in the brick doing works does not fulfill the function of the air copy, as a result of which the thermal technical characteristics of the product are reduced. It is possible to use special solutions during the construction of walls made of ceramic tiles or blocks. However, the thermal insulation properties of such solutions are estimated to be 4-5 times less than the properties of materials used in wall constructions. The thermal insulation properties of the roof coverings are explained in detail in the constructions of the public sector. Because of this, printing plays an important role in thermal insulation works. If the thermal insulation of the roof coverings is good, then additional equipment is not required to maintain the atmosphere of the working environment.

We can satisfy the demand for effective, high-strength, and bio-resistant heat insulation building solutions of the building complex by using solutions containing polyoxylgen vermiculite. Such solutions can improve the quality of construction works and environmental cleanliness with minimal material and physical resources [3].

Multi-flammable vermiculite is obtained by burning in vermiculite furnaces with fine sand. When vermiculite is heated to a temperature of 1000 °C, it becomes a crystallized clay, and as a result, it expands (enlarges) quickly. The water-induced pud has a perpendicular effect on the fracture planes, and the mica plates are separated from each other, and the size of the particles increases by 6-15 times. After being diluted, vermiculite retains its weight as a result of the air between the mica plates. Multi-inflammable vermiculite is an odorless, scaly, soft, coarse-textured material. Vermiculite has a good sound and heat insulation properties, but it also has the properties of compressibility in a very large volume. Vermiculite can absorb up to 500% of liquid by weight. However, the vermiculite liquid was well absorbed, and it almost didn't go away. Air permeability is around 100%, and vermiculite permeability can be as low as 10%.

In the works of research, multi-functional vermiculite with a particle size of 0.6 mm was used. This vermiculite fully meets the GOST 31189-2000 standard.

Thermal technical properties of multi-expandable vermiculite are presented in the table below.

1-table

Faction	Zbulk density kg/m ³	Termal conductivity λ, Vt/m·°C
VKT-1	120	0,076
VKT-2	90	0,056-0,059

One of the disadvantages of multi-fertilizing vermiculite is that its particles are in a rough shape, it has poor liquid absorption, and the mixture of solutions does not have the ability to be jetted. In addition, the low mechanical strength of vermiculite particles due to the weak connection

between separate layers has an adverse effect on the adhesion of solutions. Finally, it is recommended to use fractionated vermiculites, because such fractions are cheap and expensive.

To improve vermiculite properties, it is possible to add different types of components. They must have the following properties.

Plasticizing compounds have water-reducing properties, and the vermiculite particles present in the aggregates help to improve the water/cement ratio. As a result, the viscosity of the solution increased, as well as the strength indicators.

The viscosity of the particles with the air self-gravity effect affects the viscosity of the solution. The one in the solution is characterized by the kernel effect, the thermal conductivity of the solution.

Adhesion properties are affected not only by the adhesion properties, but also by the adhesion properties between vermiculite particles.

In Research work, the effect of additives on solutions in vermiculite was studied. In order to compare the results, a standard sample of 10-12 cm diameter was prepared. The admixtures were selected in proportion to the cement mass. A cement/vermiculite ratio of 1/1 was used in samples of ½.

2-table

Covenants	Quality of the covenants, %	Water, ml	Cement/vermiculite	Water cement layer	Spreading, sm
Megaplast K12	0,5	187,5	1:1	0,65	9
Megaplast K12	0,3	190,0	1:1	0,67	10
Polyplast SP-1	0,1	190,0	1:1	0,65	10
Polyplast SP-1	0,22	190,0	1:1	0,65	10
Polyplast SP-3	0,5	184,0	1:1	0,61	9
C-3	0,8	160,0	1:1	0,53	21
C-3	0,6	150,0	1:1	0,52	16
C-3	0,6	150	1:1	0,5	15
C-3	0,6	145	1:1	0,49	9
Polyplast SP-1	0,1%	130	1:1	0,42	11,5
Polyplast SP-1	0,1	130	1:1	0,45	10,0
Megaplast K12	0,5	130	1:1	0,44	9,5
-	-	330	1:2	1,13	11

S-3	0,6	200	1:2	0,66	7,5
Polyplast SP-1	0,8	220	1:2	0,75	12
C-3	0,8	230	1:2	0,79	10
Polyplast SP-1	1,0	220	1:2	0,75	11
Polyplast SP-1	1,0	270	1:2	0,75	11
C-3	1,0	280	1:2	0,78	10,5
Polyplast SP-1	0,6	205	1:1	0,43	20
Polyplast SP-1	0,6	190	1:1	0,4	12
C-3	0,6	187	1:1	0,4	12

Based on the obtained results, the optimal combination of vermiculite solutions with superplasticizers can be said to be C-3 and Poliplast SP-1 superplasticizers with a ratio of 0.8% by cement mass. The viscosity of the solutions of this composition was determined along with the strength of the heat transfer principle. The initial value of such solutions was 0.185 Kcal/mK, and after adding superplasticizers, this value was equal to 0.140 Kcal/mK.

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